

ETHNOMEDICINAL DOCUMENTATION ON MATERNAL AND CHILD HEALTH FROM THE IRULAR TRIBES OF CHENGALPET DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU

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ABSTRACT

Background- The Irular tribe of Tamil Nadu, India. one of the state's recognized primitive ethnic tribal groups, has preserved the wealth of ethnomedicinal knowledge. Their practices emphasize ritualistic healing, diagnostic methods, customized care during pregnancy, childbirth, and infancy rooted in Siddha tradition. This article documents and analyzes the cultural and therapeutic dimensions of these practices, highlighting with relevance to community health and potential scientific value. An ethnomedicinal survey was undertaken in order to document data about medicinal plants and animals for maternal and child health care. **Aim-** The aim of the study is to document the ethnomedicinal practices for maternal and child health care among the ethnic Irular tribe of Tamil Nadu. **Materials and Methods-** The Ethnomedicinal study was done among the Irular

community of Chengalpet District, Tamil Nadu. The data were collected using Questionnaire, Interviews through analysis with tribal people. **Discussion-** Irular practices reveal a holistic approach integrating rituals, diet, and herbal medicine. Anti-natal and Post-natal care, the dietary Regimen followed by the traditional healers is perfectly designed, to prevent co-morbidities in events of childbirth. Healers concentrate more on geriatric ailments since it is an essential need of the hour. **Results-** The result of this ethnomedicinal study has revealed

that plant species belonging to many Families were practiced by Irulas rendering personalized child care and overall health care of the society. They primarily use Roots and Whole Plants for rejuvenation in Maternal health care. **Conclusion-** This study showed the unique knowledge of Irulars of Chengalpet region in medicinal plants who renders services in women health care enhancing community wellbeing.

KEYWORDS: pregnancy, Antenatal care, Postnatal care, Neonatal practices, Geriatric care, Indigenous knowledge, rejuvenation, well-being.

INTRODUCTION

Right from the beginning of history, plant resources are considered as important aspect of human society. According to WHO (World Health Organization) more than 80% global population depends on traditional medicinal practices for their basic healthcare needs. The knowledge of medicinal plants has evolved over centuries in India, shaped by diverse traditional systems such as Ayurveda, Unani, and Siddha. In India alone, traditional healers are reported to use around 2,500 plant species, of which about 100 species are considered primary sources of medicine. Over the past few decades, Identification of medicinal plants and their traditional applications has grown significantly across the world. Documenting this indigenous knowledge through ethnomedical studies is vital for both the conservation and sustainable utilization of biological resources to the society. The Irulars are one among the 36 recognized primitive tribes of Tamil Nadu and represent the second largest tribal community in the state. Tribes in Tamil Nadu are generally classified into three categories based on their landscapes: Hill Tribes, Plain Tribes, and Nomadic or Semi-nomadic Tribes. The Irulars belong to the Plain Tribe category. They are primarily distributed across the districts of Kanchipuram, Chengalpattu, and Thiruvallur, with secondary populations in Villupuram, Thiruvannamalai, and Cuddalore. Among these regions, the Irulars of Kanchipuram, Chengalpattu, and Thiruvallur possess greater traditional medicinal knowledge, largely influenced by the geographical conditions that support the growth of diverse medicinal plants and rich biodiversity.

In particular, Chengalpattu District, especially the Thiruporur block, is notable for its abundance of medicinal herbs and the community's extensive knowledge of their use. This study documents the Irular's ethnomedicinal practices related to ritual healing, antenatal care, postnatal recovery, and neonatal well-being. These practices offer valuable insights into

community health strategies that integrate diet, herbal medicine, ritual, and lifestyle modifications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

A descriptive, cross-sectional study was undertaken among members of the Irular community residing in Chengalpet Taluk, Chengalpet District, Tamil Nadu.

Study Period

The research was conducted over a span of four months.

Study Population

Participants included traditional medicinal practitioners and tribal individuals belonging to the Irular community in the specified geographic region.

Sampling Technique

A snowball sampling technique was employed to recruit study participants. This non-probability sampling method begins with a convenience sample of initial participants (“seeds”), who then provide referrals to additional eligible members of the population, expanding the sample in successive waves. Snowball sampling is particularly suited for studies involving hard-to-reach or closely networked populations, such as traditional healers and tribal communities.

Data Collection

Data was collected through direct, face-to-face interviews with both traditional practitioners and tribal community members. Interviews were structured to capture information about traditional medicinal knowledge and practices, especially those pertaining to prenatal and postnatal care. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to the interviews.

Data Collection Procedure

Interviews were conducted in the native language of participants in settings comfortable to them, facilitating free and detailed sharing of traditional knowledge. Responses were recorded in field notes to preserve the nuances of community practices. Ethical approval and necessary permissions were obtained from relevant local authorities prior to the commencement of the data collection.

The study population comprised married women who had experienced traditional practices involving the use of medicinal plant products during the prenatal and postnatal period. In addition, women caretakers possessing traditional knowledge related to postnatal care of mother and new born baby it includes details regarding the ingredients of herbal formulations, methods of preparation, period of consumption, and associated dietary regimens and expected effects.

A questionnaire-based survey was carried out in selected villages, with groups consisting of women participating in the interviews. This approach facilitated the collection of comprehensive data on prenatal, postnatal and neonatal medicinal practices and medicinal plant use within the community.

Mother And Child Health Care Service Of Irular Tribes

During the pre-natal period along with postnatal period, the mother and newborn received dedicated care and attention from household members. Due to limited access to hospitalization facilities common among the tribal community studied, traditional home-based care practices were predominantly followed. The new mother and infant were not given confined environment for rest period due to the with-held responsibilities of their family duty.

Cultural beliefs associated with childbirth influenced household behavior and social practices. For instance, family members abstained from visiting temples, social functions, and parties for a period of 30 days, as childbirth was culturally perceived to be linked with impurity. Following this seclusion period, purification rituals were performed in their traditional Naagathamman temple.

Throughout the postnatal period, special care was provided to both mother and newborn, emphasizing the importance of hygiene and health. Herbal formulations prepared by trained village women are collected from nearby agricultural land fields and foot hills played a significant role in mitigating health risks and promoting recovery. These formulations served as both preventive restorative and palliative remedy during this vulnerable period. Medicinal plants and their formulations reflect indigenous knowledge systems and underscore the community's reliability on herbal medicine for gestational, maternal and neonatal health management. Since these practices are easily adaptable one, this traditional healing knowledge has been passed on from generation to generation.

Ethnomedicinal Plants Used During Pre-Natal Period

Ethnomedicinal prenatal care elegantly combines traditional knowledge and natural remedies to promote maternal and fetal well-being, alleviate pregnancy discomforts, and prepare the mother for childbirth through holistic and culturally rooted practices. The period of pregnancy till the delivery of baby is termed as Pre-Natal Period.

- *Zingiber officinale* (Ginger)

A traditional syrup for treating nausea during pregnancy is prepared by mixing 10 parts of ginger juice with 7 parts of milk, to which sugar crystals are added. This mixture is made into a syrup and administered before bedtime. The recommended dosage ranges from 2 to 8 grams of the syrup, taken with warm water. It is used as a general tonic.

- *Aegle marmelos* (Vilvam)

A decoction prepared with about 25 grams of roots boiled in 200 ml of water is taken twice daily during vomiting episodes to relieve nausea in first trimester.

- *Emblica officinalis* (Amla)

Fresh amla fruits soaked in honey are consumed daily, one fruit at a time, to prevent anemia and reduce nausea during pregnancy.

- *Evolvulus ulsinoides* (Vishnugrandhi)

Approximately 10 to 15 grams of flowers are ground with honey and shaped into pills about the size of a black peppercorn. These pills are taken with warm water for 3 to 5 days to manage hemorrhage.

- *Nepeta cataria* (Karpooravalli)

Leaves are cooked and consumed to prevent vomiting during pregnancy.

- *Mullugo pentaphylla* (Parpadagam)

A decoction prepared from 50 grams of the whole plant is administered as three teaspoons thrice daily for seven days to facilitate delivery.

- *Ocimum gratissimum* (Kaatu Thulasi)

Leaves of Kaatu Thulasi, combined with leaves of *Mentha arvensis* (Pudhina) and 2 teaspoons of *Trachyspermum ammi* (Oomam), are boiled together to prepare a decoction used to relieve abdominal pain.

- *Rubia cordifolia* (Manjitti)

A decoction of the plant is prepared with the addition of 100 grams of jaggery. It is consumed during pregnancy to treat anemia and improve blood circulation.

- *Vitis vinifera* (Panneer Drakshai)

Juice made by grinding grapes and their seeds and then filtered is sweetened with honey. This preparation is given during the last three months of pregnancy to relieve constipation and nausea.

- *Trigonella foenum-graecum* (Vendhayam)

Two teaspoons of fenugreek seeds boiled in a glass of milk are taken at bedtime to alleviate back pain.

- *Wedelia chinensis* (Manjal karisalai)

A 5 ml decoction of *Wedelia chinensis* mixed with water is administered on an empty stomach daily for a continuous period of 21 days to treat uterine bleeding.

- *Achyranthes aspera* (Naayuruvi)

Leaf powder of *Achyranthes aspera* is mixed with water and taken orally before delivery. Traditionally, it is believed to promote labor; however, scientific studies have indicated anti-fertility and abortifacient properties at higher doses, so caution is advised.

- *Aloe vera* (Katraazhai)

The leaf pulp of *Aloe vera* is consumed two days before delivery to facilitate and promote labor.

- *Gloriosa superba* (Kalappai kizhangu)

A fresh root paste is applied topically to the suprapubic region and vaginal area to induce labor.

Ethnomedicinal Plants Used During Post-Natal Period

Ethnomedicinal postnatal care uses traditional herbs, massages, and diets to support the mother's recovery and newborn's health after delivery, focusing on healing, nourishment, and protection during the postpartum period.

- *Rauvolfia serpentina* (Sarpagandha)

Used for its uterine stimulant properties to promote uterine contractions and facilitate fetus expulsion.

- *Achyranthes aspera* (Naayuruvi)

The whole plant is crushed and boiled in coconut oil and administered orally to cleanse the uterus over several days.

- *Aloe vera* (Katraazhai)

Leaf pulp combined with turmeric paste is applied topically on breasts to reduce nipple swelling.

- *Adathoda vasica* (Aadathodai)

Dried leaves boiled to make a decoction taken orally to prevent postpartum hemorrhage.

- *Asparagus racemosus* (Thaner vittan)

Fresh tuber juice ingested twice daily for multiple weeks to induce and promote lactation.

- *Capsicum frutescens* (Seeni milagai)

Fruit mixed with dried coconut to prepare chutney, eaten to promote uterine cleansing.

- *Carica papaya* (Papaya)

Tender fruit cooked with rice or finger millet is consumed for about a week to improve milk production.

- *Costus speciosus* (Koshtam)

Root powder taken with cold water twice daily for several days to strengthen the uterus. Studies indicate extracts stimulate uterine contractions via non-estrogenic mechanisms.

- *Ficus benghalensis* (Aalamaram)

Dried seeds ground to powder and mixed with milk, consumed to promote lactation.

- *Hemidesmus indicus* (Nannari)

Paste of fresh root taken twice daily for a short duration to enhance mother's milk production.

- *Ipomoea digitata* (Nilapoosani)

Tuber juice mixed with milk is consumed to promote lactation.

- *Mimosa pudica* (Thottar Sirungi)

A teaspoon of root paste mixed with honey is traditionally administered early each morning for seven consecutive days to be believed to promote uterine contractions and support postpartum recovery.

- *Moringa oleifera* (Murungai)

It is a natural galactagogue traditionally consumed as a curry cooked with coconut oil to boost Mother's milk production and maternal nutrition postpartum.

- *Plumbago zeylanica* (Kodiveli)

Kodiveli tuber juice is traditionally used to stimulate uterine contraction and aid in the removal of the placenta after delivery.

- *Terminalia arjuna* (Marutham pattai)

The powdered form of different plant parts is administered with honey for a duration of one week in the management of hemorrhage.

- *Tephrosia purpurea* (Kozhinji)

A decoction prepared from the leaves (5 ml), combined with honey (2 ml), is administered twice daily for one month to alleviate postnatal complications.

Ethnomedicinal Plants Used During Neo-Natal Period

The critical period of adaptability and changing phase of newborn baby is called Neo-Natal Period. This period generally lasts for the period of 4 weeks (28 days). This is the period where the newborn gets adaptable to environmental condition after getting out of the womb of mother.

- Blue Bead Chain or Garlic Thread

Tie a blue bead chain or garlic thread around the neck of newborns as a protective measure against the evil eye.

- Restricted Movement

The baby is traditionally not allowed to leave the house for one month to protect them from negative influences.

- Drying Clothes

Avoid drying the baby's clothes outside the house to prevent exposure to harmful energies.

- Protective Items

Keep broom, charcoal, chili, and iron at the doorstep as safeguards against the evil eye.

- Neem Leaves

Give the newborn a bath using boiled water infused with neem leaves. Neem leaves along with religious books are kept near the infant to invoke spiritual safety.

- Kajal Application

Apply kajal to the eyes of the newborn as a traditional protective measure.

- Oil Instillation

Sesame oil is instilled in the nostrils and ears as a preventive practice against illness in newborns. Sesame oil is valued for its nourishing, antibacterial, and protective properties, making it suitable for delicate infant skin and health maintenance.

- Urai Mathirai

It is a traditional Siddha polyherbal formulation made by grinding purified herbs like Vasambu (Sweet Flag), Jathikai (Nutmeg), and Paal Perungayam (Asafoetida in milk) on a stone. It is used to boost immunity, improve digestion, and treat common respiratory and digestive ailments in infants.

- Vengai Paal Pottu

Vengai Paal Pottu is a traditional black pottu made from the milk or resin of the Vengai tree (*Pterocarpus marsupium*). It is applied to the forehead, cheeks, or soles of newborns' feet to protect them from the evil eye (drishti). This natural preparation is free from chemicals, safe for delicate infant skin, has a pleasant aroma, and does not cause allergies. It is used since birth ceremonies, as it is easy to apply and remove, serving as a cultural protective mark rather than eye makeup.

Bathing and Hygiene Practices

- **Ritual Baths**

Newborns often undergo a ceremonial bath on the 9th or 11th day postpartum, viewed as a purification rite. Turmeric powder is applied, and the baby's hair is washed using traditional agents like shikakai or chickpea flour.

- **Herbal Bathwater**

Bathwater may be infused with neem leaves, salt, or stones for their antiseptic and protective qualities.

- **Hair Drying**

After bathing, the baby's hair is sometimes dried using fumes from burning incense or garlic, believed to ward off negativity.

- **Massage**

Infant massage is commonly practiced to relieve body aches, enhance skin softness and shine, and promote longer, restful sleep.

Cultural Beliefs and Rituals Practices

- **Post-Natal Confinement**

Newborns are traditionally confined to a separate room for a prescribed period. Household members avoid public functions and temples to prevent contact with post-birth "impurities."

Protection from Evil Spirits

Keeping the baby warm and well-covered serves both for comfort and as protection from harmful spiritual influences.

Meat, fish, and other non-vegetarian foods are usually avoided for children until they reach five years of age due to traditional beliefs about their digestibility and health impact. In exceptional cases, white goat meat may be given to the mother and recommended for the child, as it is considered light and nutritious, supporting recovery and growth during early childhood.

Key medicinal plants commonly used in traditional antenatal care, especially among tribal and indigenous communities across various regions, include:

Allium sativum (Garlic): Helps with urinary tract infections and respiratory ailments.

Moringa oleifera: Provides essential vitamins and minerals, aids in increasing milk production, and prevents anemia.

Vernonia amygdalina: Enhances breast milk flow and acts as an antibiotic for infants.

Azadirachta indica (Neem): Used for regaining strength and muscle contraction after childbirth.

Jatropha curcas: Employed to strengthen the mother and ease labor.

Ocimum gratissimum (Basil): Used for its antimicrobial properties.

Thymus linearis (Thyme): Used for colds, stomach issues, and urinary infections.

Mentha piperita (Peppermint): Used for bloating and stomach aches.

Trigonella foenum-graecum (Fenugreek): Used to stimulate milk production and improve maternal nutrition.

Cinnamomum verum (Cinnamon): Used for digestive health and blood circulation.

Salvia fruticosa (Sage): Employed for relaxing and cramp relief.

These plants are typically prepared in forms such as decoctions, infusions, or powders and administered during pregnancy for preventive, restorative, and palliative purposes. Traditional use targets common antenatal issues such as anemia, digestive problems, infections, and preparation for childbirth, reflecting strong indigenous knowledge systems in maternal healthcare.

ETHNOMEDICINAL PLANTS USED DURING PRE-NATAL PERIOD

Local Name	Botanical Name	Family	Parts Used	Uses
Inji	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome/juice	Syrup with milk & sugar to treat nausea
Vilvam	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	Rutaceae	Root	Decoction for vomiting & nausea
Nellikai	<i>Emblica officinalis</i>	Phyllanthaceae	Fruit	Prevents anemia, reduces nausea
Vishnugrandhi	<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i>	Convolvulaceae	Flowers	Pills for hemorrhage

Karpooravalli	<i>Nepeta cataria</i>	Lamiaceae	Leaves	Cooked to prevent vomiting
Parpadagam	<i>Mullugo pentaphylla</i>	Molluginaceae	Whole plant	Decoction to facilitate delivery
Kaatu Thulasi	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>	Lamiaceae	Leaves	Decoction for abdominal pain
Manjitti	<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>	Rubiaceae	Whole plant	Decoction with jaggery for anemia
Panneer Drakshai	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Vitaceae	Fruit & seeds	Juice with honey for constipation, nausea
Vendhayam	<i>Trigonella foenum-graecum</i>	Fabaceae	Seeds	Seeds in milk for back pain
Manjal Karisalai	<i>Wedelia chinensis</i>	Asteraceae	Whole plant	Decoction for uterine hemorrhage
Naayuruvi	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	Amaranthaceae	Leaves	Leaf powder before delivery to promote labor
Katraazhai	<i>Aloe vera</i>	Asphodelaceae	Leaf pulp	Taken before delivery to ease labor
Kalappai Kizhangu	<i>Gloriosa superba</i>	Colchicaceae	Root	Paste applied to induce labor

ETHNOMEDICINAL PLANTS USED DURING POST-NATAL PERIOD

Local Name	Botanical Name	Family	Parts Used	Uses
Sarpagandha	<i>Rauvolfia serpentina</i>	Apocynaceae	Root	Uterine stimulant, fetus expulsion
Naayuruvi	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	Amaranthaceae	Whole plant	Crushed in oil to cleanse uterus
Katraazhai	<i>Aloe vera</i>	Asphodelaceae	Leaf pulp	With turmeric for breast swelling
Aadathodai	<i>Adathoda vasica</i>	Acanthaceae	Leaves	Decoction to prevent hemorrhage
Thaneer Vittan	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Asparagaceae	Tuber	Fresh juice to induce lactation
Seeni Milagai	<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>	Solanaceae	Fruit	Chutney for uterine cleansing
Papaya	<i>Carica papaya</i>	Caricaceae	Tender fruit	Cooked with rice to promote lactation
Koshtam	<i>Costus speciosus</i>	Costaceae	Root powder	Strengthens uterus, aids contractions
Aalamaram	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i>	Moraceae	Seeds	Powder with milk to enhance lactation
Nannari	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i>	Apocynaceae	Root	Root paste for milk production
Nilapoosani	<i>Ipomoea digitata</i>	Convolvulaceae	Tuber	Juice with milk for lactation

Thottar Sirungi	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Fabaceae	Root	Paste with honey for uterine recovery
Murungai	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Moringaceae	Leaves	Curry with oil to boost milk
Kodiveli	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	Plumbaginaceae	Tuber	Stimulates uterine contraction, placenta expulsion
Marutham Pattai	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>	Combretaceae	Bark	Powder with honey for hemorrhage
Kozhinji	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i>	Fabaceae	Leaves	Decoction for postnatal complications

ETHNOMEDICINAL PLANTS USED DURING NEO-NATAL PERIOD

Local Name	Botanical Name	Family	Parts Used	Uses
Vepam	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Meliaceae	Leaves	Bath infusion for antiseptic protection
Ellu Ennai	<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	Pedaliaceae	Oil	In nostrils & ears for immunity
Vasambu	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	Acoraceae	Rhizome	In Urai Mathirai for digestion, immunity
Jathikai	<i>Myristica fragrans</i>	Myristicaceae	Seed	In Urai Mathirai for digestion, sleep
Paal Perungayam	<i>Ferula asafoetida</i>	Apiaceae	Resin	In Urai Mathirai for colic & digestion
Vengai	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i>	Fabaceae	Resin/milk	Applied as pottu to protect infant
Manjal	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome powder	Applied during ritual baths
Shikakai	<i>Acacia concinna</i>	Fabaceae	Pods	Natural shampoo for infant bathing
Kadalai Mavu	<i>Cicer arietinum</i>	Fabaceae	Seed flour	Used to wash baby's body & hair

Pie chart

DISCUSSION

This ethnomedicinal survey among the ethnic Irular tribe of Tamil Nadu recorded 38 medicinal plant species used in maternal and child healthcare traditionally. Among these, 14 species (36.8%) were employed during the pre-natal period, 15 species (39.5%) during the post-natal period, and 9 species (23.7%) during the neo-natal period. This distribution highlights that the largest proportion of remedies were used in post-natal care, reflecting the community's emphasis on maternal recovery, lactation enhancement, and uterine cleansing after childbirth.

Among the plant parts used, roots and tubers accounted for the majority (41%), followed by leaves (29%), and whole plant use (15%). Fruits, seeds, and other parts contributed the remaining 15%. The preference for underground parts (roots/tubers) suggests a cultural belief

in their concentrated potency for restorative purposes. The importance of Mother Child Health Care during the periods of Pre Natal, Post Natal and Neo Natal care has been focused primarily by them.

These findings indicate that traditional healers focus not only on therapeutic recovery but also on preventive and protective measures. Neo-natal practices particularly combine rituals (blue bead, garlic thread, drishti remedies) with herbal applications, illustrating the Irular's holistic view of health that integrates physical, spiritual, and cultural well-being.

CONCLUSION

This study documents of ethnic Irular community's significant ethnomedicinal knowledge, with 39.5% of plants used in post-natal care, 36.8% in pre-natal care, and 23.7% in neo-natal care. The reliance on roots and leaves emphasizes the importance of preserving biodiversity in their local environment. These practices demonstrate a well-structured traditional health system aimed at ensuring safe childbirth, maternal recovery, and infant protection. The results underline the biostatistical relevance of ethnomedicinal diversity in maternal and child health. Preserving this indigenous knowledge is essential not only for cultural continuity but also as a potential source for developing new plant-based therapeutics in modern healthcare. Practicing and Preventing the knowledge of traditional method in a scientific way may opens the doors of Healthy society in the Holistic way.

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